

Dual-Hop Hybrid Communication for Underwater and Terrestrial Systems: A Study on VLC and RF/FSO/THz Integration

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Abstract—This paper presents an analysis of dual-hop hybrid communication systems that integrate Visible Light Communication (VLC) for underwater transmission with three different terrestrial communication technologies. Specifically, we compare the performance of VLC with radio frequency (RF), free space optics (FSO), and terahertz (THz) communication in a cooperative framework involving a floating buoy as a relay node. Our results demonstrate that the THz-VLC combination significantly outperforms both the RF-VLC and FSO-VLC configurations in terms of Outage Probability (OP) and overall system efficiency. This work provides valuable insights into optimizing communication pathways in hybrid underwater-terrestrial environments, highlighting the potential of THz technology for enhanced data transmission.

Index Terms—Outage Probability (OP), Dual-Hop Communication, Hybrid Systems, Terahertz (THz) Communication, and Visible Light Communication (VLC).

I. INTRODUCTION

The vast and largely uncharted ocean covers 70% of the Earth's surface, yet more than 80% remains unexplored, a paradox given our comparatively detailed knowledge of distant planets. Understanding the ocean is crucial for addressing global challenges, from conservation of biodiversity to climate regulation [1]. However, the harsh and complex underwater environment makes exploration difficult, particularly in communication and data transfer. Traditional underwater communication technologies, such as Radio Frequency (RF) and Acoustic methods, face significant limitations: RF signals are rapidly absorbed, severely restricting range, while acoustic signals, although capable of reaching longer distances, suffer from low bandwidth, high latency, and

vulnerability to interference. These limitations hinder effective high-resolution data collection and real-time monitoring. Visible Light Communication (VLC) emerges as a promising alternative, leveraging water transparency to visible light to enable high-speed, low-latency communication, thus offering an efficient solution to the challenges of underwater exploration [1]–[3].

However, despite its advantages, VLC faces challenges in practical application due to interference by sunlight in terrestrial environments and a limited range in turbid waters. To overcome these limitations, hybrid systems that use VLC for underwater communication have been developed while relying on conventional technologies for surface transmission through a cooperative relay structure. This approach takes advantage of the strengths of VLC while effectively addressing its environmental constraints [1], [4].

Several studies have investigated hybrid RF/UVLC systems, where RF is utilized for the terrestrial hop and VLC for the underwater segment [5]–[7]. This configuration effectively addresses the limitations of VLC in terrestrial environments. However, it introduces a significant challenge: the limited data rate of the RF link creates a bottleneck, thereby constraining the performance of the underwater VLC link. Although this hybrid approach takes advantage of the robustness of RF for terrestrial communication and the high data rates of VLC for underwater transmission, the lower bandwidth of the RF link imposes a trade-off between addressing terrestrial challenges and managing data rate limitations. A potential solution to this bottleneck is to replace RF with higher-bandwidth technology. Previous studies have explored the use of Free Space Optics (FSO) instead of RF for the terrestrial link in UVLC systems [5], [8]. However, FSO, operating at frequencies above 300 GHz, is highly sensitive to atmospheric attenuation caused by weather conditions such as fog, smog, and rain, which can severely degrade overall system performance.

This paper extends our previous work [2], [9], which

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proposed a Terahertz (THz) VLC system for indoor environments, by adapting the concept to underwater VLC. Specifically, the study employs THz communication for the terrestrial link in hybrid UVLC systems. Operating in the 0.1 to 10 THz frequency band, THz communication provides key advantages such as abundant bandwidth, low latency, and high directional gain. However, it is challenged by high path loss, pointing errors, and molecular absorption [2], [9]. To address absorption losses, this study leverages THz communication in a lower frequency range. Although substantial research has focused on cooperative relay-assisted RF-UVLC and FSO-UVLC configurations, to the best of the authors' knowledge, no prior work has analyzed the performance of cooperative relay-assisted THz-UVLC systems. This paper advances the previous concept by proposing a straightforward yet effective approach to mitigate absorption losses, thus enhancing the efficiency of the system in underwater environments.

The key contributions of this paper are as follows:

- Introduction of a dual-hop communication system that employs a decode-and-forward relay architecture, with THz communication used in the first hop and UVLC in the second hop.
- Presentation of simulation results to evaluate the performance of the proposed system, along with a comparative analysis of the outage Probability performance between the proposed system and FSO-UVLC and RF-UVLC configurations, highlighting the benefits of combining THz with UVLC.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Fig. 1 shows the system model, where a surface buoy equipped with a decode-and-forward (DF) relay network serves as the interface between the underwater VLC link and the terrestrial link. In the first hop, the signal is transmitted from the boat to the surface buoy using either an RF, FSO, or THz link. In the second hop, the signal is relayed from the buoy to the Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) using VLC. It is important to clarify that THz, FSO, and RF are shown together in the figure not to suggest that all three are used simultaneously but to represent the experimental setup designed to identify the most suitable terrestrial communication technology. For the first hop, Binary Phase Shift Keying (BPSK) is used as the modulation scheme, while On-Off Keying (OOK) is employed for the second hop involving UVLC.

The practical implementation of THz-VLC systems presents several challenges, particularly regarding beam alignment, relay positioning, and real-time channel adaptation [2]. THz communication relies on highly directional beams, which can suffer from misalignment due to environmental disturbances or hardware limitations [9]. To mitigate this, mechanical beam steering mechanisms, MEMS-based reconfigurable optics, and UAV-assisted relay positioning can be used [10], [11]. Furthermore, while experimental validation is

beyond the scope of this study, the existing literature on THz and VLC testbeds demonstrates its feasibility in controlled environments [12], [13]. Future work will focus on hardware implementation and field trials to further validate simulation-based findings.

The following system-level equations describe the communication links in the dual-hop relay system:

$$Y_{sr} = \sqrt{P_{src}} H_{THz} x + n_{SR}, \quad (1)$$

$$Y_{rd} = \sqrt{P_{relay}} H_{UVLC} \tilde{x} + n_{RD}, \quad (2)$$

where, P_{src} denotes the source power, P_{relay} represents the relay power, H_{THz} is the channel gain for the THz link from the source to the relay, and H_{UVLC} is the channel gain for the UVLC link from the relay to the destination. The variable x represents the transmitted information signal, while \tilde{x} denotes the signal encoded by the relay. Furthermore, n_{SR} and n_{RD} represent the noise introduced in the source-to-relay and relay-to-destination links, respectively.

A. THz Channel Model

The gain for the Terahertz (THz) communication channel can be modeled as follows [2]:

$$H_{THz} = g_{fs} \cdot g_{abs} \cdot g_{mis}, \quad (3)$$

where g_{fs} , g_{abs} , and g_{mis} correspond to the free-space path loss, molecular absorption, and misalignment fading effects, respectively.

Free-space path loss for line-of-sight (LoS) transmission is expressed through the Friis transmission equation, which describes the loss as a function of the distance between the transmitter and receiver, the frequency of operation, and the antenna gains. The path loss is given by:

$$g_{fs} = \frac{c\sqrt{G_{TX}G_{RX}}}{4\pi df}, \quad (4)$$

where d represents the separation between the transmitter and receiver, f is the operating frequency, and G_{TX} and G_{RX} are the gains of the transmitting and receiving antennas, respectively.

The molecular absorption effect refers to the loss of THz signal strength caused by the absorption of specific molecules, such as O_2 and H_2O , in the atmosphere. This loss is especially significant at certain THz frequencies, where these molecules absorb part of the electromagnetic energy. The attenuation due to molecular absorption is given by:

$$g_{abs} = e^{-\frac{1}{2}\kappa(f)d}, \quad (5)$$

where $\kappa(f)$ represents the absorption coefficient, which quantifies the amount of energy absorbed by the medium at a specific frequency f , and d is the distance.

In the THz communication system, directional antenna systems are used, which can experience misalignment due to environmental disturbances or physical movements, such

Fig. 1. The proposed dual-hop hybrid THz-VLC system for underwater and terrestrial communication. The first hop utilizes a THz/FSO/RF link to transmit data from a surface vessel to a floating buoy relay, while the second hop employs VLC to forward data to an AUV. The figure highlights different first-hop configurations to evaluate the optimal terrestrial communication technology for integration with VLC.

as building sway. This misalignment causes errors in the pointing direction of the antennas [2]. The effective beam width due to misalignment can be expressed as:

$$w_{\text{eq}} = \sqrt{w_d^2 \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \operatorname{erf}(u)}{2u \exp(-u^2)}}, \quad (6)$$

where w_d is the beam waist, and u is the normalized beam radius given by $u = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}a}{\sqrt{2}w_d}$, with a being the radius of the receiver's circular aperture.

The misalignment gain can be approximated as:

$$g_{\text{mis}}(r) \approx A_0 \exp\left(-\frac{2r^2}{w_{\text{eq}}^2}\right), \quad (7)$$

where A_0 is the fraction of power collected by the receiver, expressed as $A_0 = (\operatorname{erf}(u))^2$. The probability density function (PDF) for misalignment fading is given by:

$$f_{g_{\text{mis}}}(x) = \frac{\xi^2}{A_0^{\xi^2}} x^{\xi^2-1}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq A_0, \quad (8)$$

where ξ is the ratio of the beam width to the standard deviation of the pointing error, defined as $\xi = \frac{w_{\text{eq}}}{2\sigma_r}$, with σ_r representing the standard deviation of the pointing error at the receiver.

B. UVLC Channel Model

The signal attenuation in the VLC link depends on the vertical line of sight (LOS) distance d_{LOS} between the AUV and the relay, as well as the extinction coefficient $c_{\text{opt}}(\lambda)$. This coefficient accounts for both absorption $a_{\text{opt}}(\lambda)$ and

scattering $b_{\text{opt}}(\lambda)$ of the optical photons in the underwater environment, with the relation $c_{\text{opt}}(\lambda) = a_{\text{opt}}(\lambda) + b_{\text{opt}}(\lambda)$. The typical values for $a_{\text{opt}}(\lambda)$ and $b_{\text{opt}}(\lambda)$ in various water types are provided in Table I. Accordingly the underwater signal attenuation according to Beer-Lambert's law can be expressed as [5]:

$$h_{\text{att}}^{\text{VLC}}(\lambda, d_{\text{LOS}}) = \exp(-c_{\text{opt}}(\lambda)d_{\text{LOS}}) \quad (9)$$

TABLE I
TYPICAL VALUES OF ABSORPTION AND SCATTERING COEFFICIENTS IN DIFFERENT WATER TYPES FOR UNDERWATER VLC

Description of Water for UWC	$a(\lambda)$	$b(\lambda)$	$c(\lambda)$
Clear Ocean Water	0.069	0.08	0.15
Pure Sea Water	0.053	0.003	0.056
Coastal Ocean Water	0.088	0.216	0.305

For the UVLC link, the effects of underwater turbulence are modeled using a generalized Gamma (GG) distribution [5]. The distribution is assumed to consist of independent, but not identically distributed, random variables. The probability density function (PDF) for the underwater turbulence can be expressed as in equation (10).

where $K_{\alpha_{\text{turb}}-\beta_{\text{turb}}}(\cdot)$ represents the modified Bessel function of the second kind. Under strong turbulence conditions, the PDF in terms of the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is given by equation (11).

In this equation, $G(\cdot)$ represents the G-Meijer function, with integer parameters m , n , p , and q , and the arguments a_p and b_q . The average electrical SNR is denoted as μ_{VLC} . The scattering and large-scale and small-scale components

$$f_{h_{\text{turb}}}(h_{\text{turb}}) = 2 \cdot \frac{(\alpha_{\text{turb}}\beta_{\text{turb}})^{\frac{\alpha_{\text{turb}}+\beta_{\text{turb}}}{2}}}{\Gamma(\alpha_{\text{turb}})\Gamma(\beta_{\text{turb}})} \cdot (h_{\text{turb}})^{\frac{\alpha_{\text{turb}}+\beta_{\text{turb}}}{2}-1} \cdot K_{\alpha_{\text{turb}}-\beta_{\text{turb}}}\left(2\sqrt{\alpha_{\text{turb}}\beta_{\text{turb}}h_{\text{turb}}}\right) \quad (10)$$

$$f_{\gamma_{\text{VLC}}}(\gamma) = \frac{\alpha_{\text{turb}}\beta_{\text{turb}}}{\Gamma(\alpha_{\text{turb}})\Gamma(\beta_{\text{turb}})} \cdot G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_{\text{turb}}\beta_{\text{turb}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_{\text{VLC}}}{\mu_{\text{VLC}}}} \mid \alpha_{\text{turb}} - 1, \beta_{\text{turb}} - 1 \right] \quad (11)$$

of both the uplink and downlink are characterized by the parameters α_{turb} and β_{turb} , respectively.

III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

If P_{src} represents the power at the source, and $\sigma_{\text{src-rel}}$ is the noise power associated with n_{SR} , then the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) for the THz link, accounting for beam misalignment, can be formulated as:

$$\gamma_{\text{THz}} = \frac{P_{\text{src}}|H_{\text{THz}}|^2}{\sigma_{\text{src-rel}}^2}. \quad (12)$$

Similarly, if P_{relay} denotes the relay's transmit power, and $\sigma_{\text{rel-dest}}$ represents the noise power in the relay-to-destination link, the SNR for the UVLC link can be given by:

$$\gamma_{\text{UVLC}} = \frac{P_{\text{relay}}|H_{\text{UVLC}}|^2}{\sigma_{\text{rel-dest}}^2}. \quad (13)$$

In the system model, an outage event occurs if the SNR of either the THz link or the UVLC link falls to or below a specific threshold denoted as γ_{thr} . This can be expressed as:

$$P_{\text{outage}} = P(\gamma_{\text{DF}} \leq \gamma_{\text{thr}}) = P(\min(\gamma_{\text{THz}}, \gamma_{\text{UVLC}}) \leq \gamma_{\text{thr}}). \quad (14)$$

Given the independence of the instantaneous SNRs for each link, as previously defined in Equations (12) and (13), the outage probability can be expanded as given in equation(15).

The scalability and robustness of the proposed THz-VLC hybrid system depend on various factors, including distance, environmental conditions, and beam alignment challenges [9]. THz signals experience significant path loss due to molecular absorption, which can limit long-range applicability. To enhance scalability, multihop relaying and intelligent reflecting surfaces (IRS) can be used to extend the THz coverage without excessive power consumption [14]. Furthermore, environmental factors such as humidity, fog, and water turbidity impact both the THz and VLC links, leading to an increased probability of outage in adverse conditions [2], [3]. To mitigate these effects, adaptive beamforming, power control, and frequency-selective transmission can dynamically optimize link performance based on environmental conditions [15], [16]. These techniques enable reliable high-speed THz-VLC communication even in dynamic and challenging scenarios, making it a promising solution for future large-scale deployments.

The computational complexity of the proposed system is mainly due to DF relay processing, channel estimation, and link switching, rather than advanced signal processing techniques. In the first hop, THz links require beam tracking and power adaptation to compensate for path loss and molecular absorption, which introduces moderate computational overhead. The second VLC hop, although less complex, must handle attenuation due to water turbidity and turbulence, which requires efficient power allocation [2], [3], [9]. From an energy perspective, THz transmission is power intensive due to high-frequency absorption, but this is mitigated by relay-assisted forwarding and adaptive power control [11], [15], [16]. In contrast, VLC-based communication is inherently energy-efficient, making it a sustainable choice for underwater data transfer [3]. The hybrid THz-VLC approach thus balances energy efficiency and computational complexity, making it a viable solution for short- to medium-range underwater-terrestrial communication.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Table II provides the value of the simulation parameters used, which were taken from [2], [5].

Parameter	Symbol	Value
THz Antenna Gain	G_{tx}, G_{rx}	$10^{5.5}$ (55 dBi)
First hop distance (THz/FSO/RF)	d_{tr}	30 m
THz Frequency	f	300×10^9 Hz
Threshold SNR	γ_{th}	4
Radius of Reception Antenna	a	0.1 m
Beam Footprint Radius	w_{d1}	0.6 m
Pointing Error Parameter	σ_s	0.05
Underwater Attenuation Coef.	c_{opt}	Table I
Wavelength	λ	1550 nm
Visibility	∇	800
Large-Scale Fading (UVLC)	α_{turb}	7.2036
Small-Scale Fading (UVLC)	β_{turb}	5.6759

TABLE II
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Fig. 2 illustrates the outage probability of the system as a function of SNR for three different first-hop technologies: FSO, RF, and THz. The simulation considers a 30 m terrestrial link and a 10 m underwater VLC link in pure seawater. The results demonstrate that the THz-UVLC configuration achieves lower outage probabilities at higher SNR values compared to FSO-UVLC and RF-UVLC. This improvement is attributed to the high available bandwidth and low latency of the THz link that allow efficient data transfer under clear conditions, despite its sensitivity to environmental factors. Although FSO can also deliver high data rates, it

$$P_{\text{outage}} = P\left(|H_{\text{THz}}|^2 \leq \frac{\gamma^{\text{thr}} \sigma_{\text{src-rel}}^2}{P_{\text{src}}}\right) + P\left(|H_{\text{UVLC}}|^2 \leq \frac{\gamma^{\text{thr}} \sigma_{\text{rel-dest}}^2}{P_{\text{relay}}}\right) - P\left(|H_{\text{THz}}|^2 \leq \frac{\gamma^{\text{thr}} \sigma_{\text{src-rel}}^2}{P_{\text{src}}}\right) \cdot P\left(|H_{\text{UVLC}}|^2 \leq \frac{\gamma^{\text{thr}} \sigma_{\text{rel-dest}}^2}{P_{\text{relay}}}\right). \quad (15)$$

Fig. 2. Outage performance of the proposed THz-UVLC system is compared with FSO-UVLC and RF-UVLC configurations over a 30 m terrestrial link and 10 m underwater link in pure seawater.

Fig. 3. Outage Probability Comparison Across Different Water Types for THz-UVLC, FSO-UVLC, and RF-UVLC Configurations.

is significantly affected by atmospheric interference due to its higher operating frequency, especially over longer link distances and at higher SNR thresholds. However, the RF link, known for its robustness against misalignment and environmental variations, has comparatively lower data rate capabilities, resulting in higher outage probabilities compared to THz and FSO.

Fig. 3 compares the probability of outage of the THz-UVLC system with the FSO-VLC and RF-VLC configurations for three types of water: pure seawater, coastal water, and coastal ocean water. The probability of a power outage increases as water turbidity increases in all configurations, with the highest power outage observed in coastal ocean water. In pure seawater, THz-UVLC performs the best at higher SNR, maintaining a low outage probability due to favorable propagation conditions for VLC supported by the high data rate of the terrestrial THz link. However, in coastal ocean water, light scattering and absorption severely degrade the UVLC link, increasing the outage probability for all configurations. The RF-VLC configuration experiences a higher outage due to its limited bandwidth and lower SNR performance.

Fig. 4 compares the outage performance of the THz-UVLC and FSO-UVLC systems under varying pointing errors, focusing on how misalignment affects the terrestrial hop. The RF-UVLC configuration is excluded since RF is not

Fig. 4. Comparison of outage probability for the proposed THz-UVLC and FSO-UVLC configurations with varying degrees of pointing errors, emphasizing the sensitivity of each system to misalignment in the terrestrial hop.

affected by pointing errors. The results show that as pointing errors increase, the outage probability increases for both THz-UVLC and FSO-UVLC, with THz-UVLC maintaining a lower outage rate across different levels of pointing error at high SNRs. This performance disparity can be attributed

to the narrower beamwidth and high directional gain of THz, which, although sensitive to misalignment, can achieve superior performance with precise alignment. FSO suffers more from pointing errors due to atmospheric attenuation and larger beam divergence, which amplifies misalignment issues over distance. These results highlight that while THz-UVLC is highly effective, it requires accurate beam alignment to fully capitalize on its bandwidth advantages, whereas FSO, though still affected, is less efficient under the same conditions.

The simulation results underscore the superior performance of the THz-UVLC hybrid communication system in terms of outage probability and overall system efficiency, especially, when compared to RF-UVLC and FSO-UVLC configurations. The THz-UVLC system, leveraging its high data rates and low latency, consistently achieves lower outage probabilities across a wide range of SNR values under clear conditions. Although the FSO-UVLC system also offers high data rates, its performance is significantly hindered by atmospheric interference, particularly at higher SNR levels and over extended link distances. The RF-UVLC configuration, while exhibiting robustness in challenging environmental conditions, falls short in data throughput and is more prone to outages under higher SNR thresholds. In scenarios considering water turbidity, the THz-UVLC system retains its performance advantage in pure seawater, though all systems experience elevated outage probabilities as water quality degrades. The system's sensitivity to pointing errors emphasizes the importance of precise alignment, particularly for the THz-UVLC system. Despite its high directional gain, the THz-UVLC configuration is more susceptible to misalignment compared to FSO-UVLC, underscoring the critical need for advanced alignment mechanisms in such high-precision communication systems.

V. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the potential of dual-hop hybrid communication systems combining THz and UVLC technologies for underwater and terrestrial communication in challenging environments. Our findings suggest that the THz-VLC combination significantly outperforms other communication technologies such as RF and FSO in terms of outage probability, particularly in ideal or low-turbidity water conditions. Although THz-UVLC shows substantial promise for high-speed, high-capacity communication in clear underwater environments, the challenges posed by misalignment, water quality, and environmental interference underscore the need for further optimization in system design and alignment strategies. Overall, this work paves the way for future advancements in hybrid communication networks, with THz technology playing a pivotal role in enhancing the reliability and throughput of underwater-terrestrial communication systems. Future work will focus on extending the analysis by comparing the proposed THz-VLC system with other poten-

tial hybrid communication techniques to further evaluate its applicability across diverse deployment scenarios.

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